

Effect of Working Environment on Job Satisfaction among Non-Teaching Staff in Secondary Schools in Keiyo South Sub-County, Kenya

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to assess the effect of remuneration and promotion on Job satisfaction among non-teaching staff in secondary schools. The theoretical framework was based on Herzberg's Two Factor Theory and McGregor Theory X and Theory Y on motivational theories. The research adopted an explanatory research design. The targeted population comprised of 408 non-teaching staff in public secondary schools in Keiyo South Sub-County, Elgeyo Marakwet County. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 202 non-teaching staff drawn from 35 high schools. Data were collected using questionnaires. Multiple regressions were used to test hypotheses. Quantitative data gathered in the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques which were frequencies means, percentages, distributions, and standard deviations. The findings from the study indicated remuneration had a significant and positive effect on job satisfaction, while promotions had an insignificant impact on job satisfaction. Thus, the study concluded that remuneration is important determinants of non-teaching staff job satisfaction in secondary schools. There is, therefore, need to ensure that employees are fairly remunerated and paid by the national government like other civil servants. Employees' qualifications together with experience need to be commensurate to their pay at all levels of the organization to enhance job satisfaction.

Keywords; Non-Teaching Staff, Remuneration, Job Satisfaction, Promotions

Introduction

An enabling and supportive work environment is one of the crucial factors which are considered to influence satisfaction and motivation level of employees in an organization. Conducive work environment contributes immensely to employees job satisfaction. Availability or absence of certain aspects of human resource policies and practices in the working environment such as fair remuneration, the opportunity for promotion and growth, open communication, training and development, and participative management style may lead to employee job satisfaction or dissatisfaction, Armstrong (2009). Okumbe (2000) argues that strong education management requires a thorough knowledge and application of motivation and job satisfaction which have been proven to be applicable in an educational setting.

The level of job satisfaction has some relation to the various aspect of work behavior such as lateness, absenteeism, labor turnover, Saari & Judge (2006), Choo & Bowley (2007), morale and poor attitude towards the performance of duty, Kiptoo (2011). Khan, Aslam & Lodhi (2011) argues that pleasant environment enhance employee job satisfaction. The non-teaching staff perceives their work and work environment as not being supportive. Improvement of employee working environment reduces complaints and absenteeism and increase productivity, Roelofsen (2002). In Kenya public secondary schools, the teaching staffs are employed, managed, and paid by the Teachers Service Commission (TSC) while the non-teaching staff is employed and managed by the Board of management at each secondary school. The Basic Education Act (2013) states that every Board of Management shall, pursuant to section 59 of the Act, recruit, employ, remunerate, promote, demote, and even terminate the services of its employees. The expansion of secondary schools has led to the engagement of much non-teaching staff by the boards of management (BOM). It is important to note that the

heads of schools and the BOM need to focus on enhancing non-teaching staff working conditions that will be conducive to their job satisfaction.

Replay 2003 asserts that an organization should pay close attention to the working conditions that will be conducive to the employee's Job Satisfaction. Both Teaching and non-teaching staff are valuable assets to any educational institution. The non-teaching staff refers to all the employees of the board of management of schools who are not engaged in teaching. The non-teaching staff comprises of senior and support staff categories which include among others bursars, accounts clerks, secretaries, nurses, cateresses, matrons, technicians, librarians, cooks, watchmen, cleaners, and artisans. They provide support surface in schools. The NTS duties are to ensure that teaching and learning environments are made favorable for the attainment of educational objectives (Okumbe, 2000)

According to a task force on student discipline in secondary schools in Kenya, Ministry of Education Science and Technology 2001 reported that non-teaching staff had no scheme of service making their salaries vary from one board to the other. This was mainly because of financial abilities that depended on fees collection, which often led to salary delays, non-remittance of statutory deduction, pilferage, and general discontent hence constant incitement of students. This implies that they are dissatisfied with their job conditions and working environment.

There is empirical proof that workplace conditions determine the rate of improvement in job satisfaction. Many studies have been carried out on the phenomena different sectors of economy globally, in education sector the focus has been on the teaching and non-teaching staff in the Universities and teachers in secondary schools for example research by Nganzi (2014), Abdulla (2009), Osakwe (2014), who have carried out studies on factors influencing job satisfaction among secondary school teachers, Azeem & Quddus (2014), Sarah, Mat and Pranavkumar (2012) and Tai (2014) have also studied on factors affecting non-teaching staff in Universities in India, Malaysia and Taiwan respectively. From the above, it is imperative that this study was carried out to establish the effect of working environment on job satisfaction among non-teaching staff in secondary schools in Keiyo South Sub-County to address the gap of limited research studies.

Additionally, non-teaching staff satisfaction with the working environment is not only important to non-teaching staff themselves but also other stakeholders in education. However, scholars and researchers have given more attention to teachers' job satisfaction as compared to those focusing on the issues about non-teaching staff job satisfaction in relations to their working environment in secondary schools in Kenya. It is in relation to the above that this study would address the gap in establishing the effects of the working environment of job satisfaction of non-teaching staff in various secondary schools.

H₀₁: Remuneration has no significant effect on Job satisfaction among non-teaching staff in secondary schools

H₀₂: Promotions have no significant effect on Job Satisfaction among non-teaching staff in secondary schools

Theoretical Background Review

To understand the effect of working environment on job satisfaction on the nonteaching staff in secondary schools, this study adopted the motivational theories. Motivations can be said to one measure of Job satisfaction (Mbua, 2003). This implies that the theories of motivation are also regarded as theories of job satisfaction. These theories applied in this study are namely Frederick Herzberg; two-factor theory and Douglas McGregor Theory X and Theory Y.

Herzberg indicated that certain factors lead to job satisfaction while others lead to dissatisfaction (Joshi, 2013). He referred the two sets as motivators and hygienic factors respectively. According to Madura (2006), Herzberg had conducted a study on 200 accountants and engineers about job satisfaction in order to find out factors contributing to their dissatisfaction towards their jobs. The motivators / satisfiers identified are recognition by others, work itself degree of career achievement, levels of job responsibility and opportunity for promotion and growth. On the other hand, he identified hygiene/ maintenance factors as working conditions, salary, and supervision, management policies and procedures, job conditions and interpersonal relationships. According to Pattanyak (2005), hygiene factors are important in preventing job dissatisfaction among the employee. Mukherjee (2009) added that motivation factors contribute to the higher level of job satisfaction.

The Herzberg two factor theories are appropriate in this study as it focuses on the two set of factors that are relevant when taken care of by the school administrators which may improve the non- teaching staff working condition job satisfaction. It is also well received and impressed by practicing managers because it makes a simple distinction between factors contributing positively to job satisfaction and those causing job dissatisfaction.

This study acknowledges the use of McGregor theory X and theory Y. He advocated that there is two set of management of attitude towards employees in the workplace which have a bearing on the level of employee motivation and job satisfaction. The first set of assumptions regards employees, as being lazy, coercion and control, requiring, avoiding responsibility, and only seeking security (Cole, 2004). He referred this management attitude as theory X. This style of management is no longer tenable in today's organizational environment.

McGregor's second set of theories saw the employees in a more favorable light, and he called this theory Y. The managers under this category see employees liking work which is natural as recreation and rest; exercise self-direction and control to achieve all the objectives they committed themselves in the workplace; Commitment objective is related to the satisfaction of achievement, and if the conditions are right, the average person at work will seek and accept responsibility (Joshi, 2013). Theory Y, he suggested can best be applied to motivate and satisfy employees where managers develop the potentials and facilitating workers to use their potentials to realize organizational objectives. The blend of theory X and theory Y may help in adopting effective management styles. This theory was appropriate for this study because leadership styles may enhance positive or negative effects in a working environment on job satisfaction among the nonteaching staff.

Related Literature Review

Effect of Remuneration on Job Satisfaction.

Beckery (2011) explains that pay adequacy has the power to attract, retain, and even motivate employees or any individual towards higher performance. Brown (2007) conducted a study to determine the effect of remuneration on job satisfaction. The research was carried out among 16266 workers and employees who work in almost 800 institutions to examine the factors of happiness at work. The results of the study indicated a number of salaries paid to employees affect the level of job satisfaction.

Other research work that was done revealed that the salary increase could influence only jobs with a low level of income but not the high-level ones, and in some cases, a raise might set back job satisfaction. Therefore, there might be some evidence to suggest that the relationship is not linear, but it's rather a curvilinear one (Ward, 2001). For example, Bender & Heywood (2004) found that university professors who earn a high income as compared to other jobs have high job satisfaction. In another study by Charles, Newsham, Brand, Donnelly & VeitchAries, (2006) on the relationship between salary and job satisfaction, the researchers concluded that there is the direct correlation between job satisfaction and pay after controlling the age variable.

This means that job satisfaction for the salary increases with age due to the low financial responsibilities with the growth of age.

In a similar study by Clark, (2001) the researchers examined data collected from more than five thousand employees. The result was that the job satisfaction declines with a high level of education. This study suggests that education has an adverse impact on job satisfaction, as the increase in the level of education leads one to higher expectations which negatively affect the job attitude and performance such a person may become dissatisfied in performing the routine tasks even when their salary might be higher than those youthful employees. Such studies may indicate that the salary does not influence job satisfaction directly but through other factors. Other studies suggest that salary amount is not important for job satisfaction but rather a comparison of income that the employees are set up as referential point (Bowles, Gintis & Osborne, 2001).

Effect of Promotions on Job Satisfaction.

Promotion involves a change where an employee moves from one job to another that carries higher status, duties, responsibilities and a higher salary. It refers to an employee being upgraded from lower grade to higher grade with greater accountability and compensation. Kosteas (2009) asserts that promotions have a positive effect on job functions and hence overall job satisfaction.

Firms can utilize promotions as a way of rewarding highly productive worker hence creating a way for other staff to exert more effort hence increasing work performance. Promotions create a positive influence on job satisfaction because other employees will want to get the same promotion hence will work even harder (Clark, 2001).

Brown, (2001) asserts that promotion creates more satisfaction among employees. It enhances job satisfaction among employees and provides them an opportunity to remain and have unbroken service in their organization. It provides psychological satisfaction to workers as their contributions are recognized and appreciated by the organizational leaders. Regarding all parameters that influence employees' careers progressions and remunerations, tournament theory stipulates that organizations use promotion to motivate their staff hence realize a high level of productivity. Francis, Cadsby, Bram, & Song (2007) argues that estimating the effect of both promotions and its effects on job satisfaction enable one to comprehend the role of promotions as a mechanism for getting greater effort from workers. Arguing that promotions lead to enhanced job satisfaction, even after controlling salaries and wage increases, it supports the assumption that employees value the promotion itself. Promotions have been seen to create more energy among employees thus leading to more job satisfaction (Andrew, 2001).

Usually, when there is enough room for promotion, workers get more job satisfaction. For highly qualified workers, the scope for promotion plays a huge role in job satisfaction than for unqualified workers. In another study by (Das, 2002) it was argued that promotion is more important for more energetic workers than old workers. When there are no promotions to the efficient and employees, there is an increased feeling of frustration hence loss of job satisfaction. Das (2002) argued that every organization should provide the scope for promotion to all the employees deserving, qualified and competent employees. Those who are satisfied with the opportunities for promotion portray high job satisfaction as compared to other employees.

Material and methods

The researcher employed an explanatory research design. The target population comprised of 408 non-teaching staff drawn from 35 public secondary schools in Keiyo South Sub-County, Elgeyo Marakwet County. The sample size was selected by using Taro Yamane (1973) formula which was modified by Kent (2008) sample

size formula to select a sample size of 202 non-teaching staff from the target population of the 408. The study used stratified sampling technique to select the non-teaching staff from each division and school where respondents were picked from. Questionnaires were used for collection of primary data from secondary schools in- teaching staff. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine a reliability index Santos & Reynold (1999). Quantitative data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical techniques which included frequencies, mean, standard deviation. Measures of central tendency gave expected summary statistics of the variables being tested. The findings were presented by the use of frequency distribution tables, which gave recorded number of times a score or a response occurs. Inferential statistics such as Pearson moment correlations were used to establish the relations between variables. Multiple regressions were used to establish the cause

FINDINGS

Job Satisfaction

This section of the analysis presents the results on job satisfaction. Table 1 illustrates the results of the study. As evidenced in the table, respondents strongly agreed that they feel a strong sense of belonging to their school (mean = 4.42, SD = 0.749). Also, agreed that they feel happy that their school does provide good health and safe working environment (mean = 4.04, SD = 0.955). Further, they are happy with their work because it offers them a sense of achievement and accomplishment (mean = 3.86, SD = 1.181). Similarly, they are happy with their school because their compensation is tied to their performance (mean = 3.83, SD = 1.133).

In addition, respondents affirmed that their school offers them an opportunity to pursue their own goals (mean = 3.7, SD = 1.137) and they feel good about their school because it utilizes all their talents and skills (mean = 3.6, SD = 1.181). As well, respondents agreed that they are happy with their school as it provides resources they need to meet their goals (mean = 3.51, SD = 1.445). However, respondents moderately agreed that they feel good because their school involves them when setting their goals /targets (mean = 3.48, SD = 1.391). In light of the aforementioned findings, it can be concluded that the non-teaching staff feels a strong sense of belonging to the school since the school utilizes their talents and skills and gives them an opportunity to pursue their own goals. There is thus a sense of achievement and accomplishment.

Table 1 **Job Satisfaction**

	Mean	Std. Deviation
I feel a strong sense of belonging to my school	4.42	0.749
I am happy with my school because my compensation is tied to my performance	3.83	1.133
I am happy with my work because it offers me a sense of achievement and accomplishment	3.86	1.181
My school offers me an opportunity to pursue my own goals	3.7	1.137
I feel good about My school because it utilizes all my talents and skills	3.6	1.181
I feel good because my school involves me when setting my goals /targets	3.48	1.391
I feel happy that my school does provide good health and safety working environment	4.04	0.955
I am happy with my school as it provides resources I need to meet my goals	3.51	1.445

Source (field data, 2015)

Remuneration and Job Satisfaction

This section of the analysis sought to establish the effect of remuneration on job satisfaction among non-teaching staff. The findings are as presented in Table 2. From the table, respondents disagreed that their pay and benefit are commensurate with their experience and skills (mean = 2.63, SD = 1.378). Moreover, they moderately agreed that they are paid fairly without favor (mean = 2.91, SD = 1.464). However, 27.9% (55) of the respondents disagreed that their gross salary is satisfactory and reasonable (mean = 2.41, SD = 1.281). Similarly, they strongly disagreed that their school provides additional incentives (mean = 2.32, SD = 1.323). Finally, respondents disagreed that their overtime pay is adequate (mean = 1.94, SD = 1.137). In light of the foregoing results, there is much to be done in regards to remuneration. Basing on the findings, the pay and benefits seem to be disproportionate to experience and skills. Thus most of the non-teaching staff doubt whether they are paid fairly without favor. Finally, there is inadequate overtime pay and unsatisfactory gross salary.

Table 2 Remuneration and job satisfaction

	Mean	Std. Deviation
Overtime pay is adequate	1.94	1.137
Our gross salary is satisfactory and reasonable	2.41	1.281
Our school provides additional incentives	2.32	1.323
We are paid fairly without favor	2.91	1.464
Pay and benefit are commensurate with my experience and skills	2.63	1.378

Source (field data, 2015)

Promotion and Job Satisfaction

In this section of the analysis, the researcher sought to establish the effect of promotion on job satisfaction. Table 3 presents the results. 51.3% (101) of the respondents strongly disagreed that their school provides promotions (mean = 2.09, SD = 1.378). However, 34% (67) of the respondents strongly disagreed that those who perform well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted (mean = 2.51, SD = 1.402). Similarly, 32% (63) of the respondents disagreed that they are satisfied with chances for promotion in their school (mean = 2.5, SD = 1.335). Further, 34% (67) of the respondents disagreed that the promotion policy is clear in the school (mean = 2.48, SD = 1.438). The aforementioned findings indicate that there is doubt whether there are policies and procedures for the training and development of non-teaching staff. It is also not certain whether the non-teaching staffs are satisfied with the chances of promotion in the school. Thus, it was revealed by the majority of the non-teaching staff that the school does not provide promotions.

Table 3 Promotion and job satisfaction

		SD	D	MA	A	SA	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our school provides promotions.	Freq.	101	38	13	29	16	2.09	1.378
	%	51.3	19.3	6.6	14.7	8.1		
Those who perform well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	Freq.	67	47	14	53	16	2.51	1.402
	%	34	23.9	7.1	26.9	8.1		
I am satisfied with chances for promotion in our school	Freq.	55	63	24	35	20	2.5	1.335
	%	27.9	32	12.2	17.8	10.2		
Promotion policy is clear in the school	Freq.	67	47	14	53	16	2.48	1.438
	%	34	23.9	7.1	26.9	8.1		

Source (field data, 2015)

Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a technique for assessing the relationship between variables: remuneration, promotion, training and development, leadership style and communication with job satisfaction. Thus, the study analyzed the relationships that are inherent among the independent and dependent variables. The results regarding this were summarized and presented in Table 4. Findings revealed that remuneration was positively and significantly associated with job satisfaction ($r = 0.553$, $\rho < 0.01$). Further, the promotion was positively and significantly correlated with job satisfaction ($r = 0.411$, $\rho < 0.01$). This implies that remunerations and promotion are expected to influence job satisfaction.

Table 4 Correlation Analysis

	Job satisfaction	Remunerations	Promotion
Job satisfaction	1		
Remunerations	.553**	1	
Promotion	.411**	.535**	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source (field data, 2015)

Regression Results/Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}) stated that remuneration has no significant effect on job satisfaction. Findings in Table 5 showed that remuneration had coefficients of estimate which was significant basing on $\beta_1 = 0.474$ (p -value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$). The null hypothesis was thus rejected, and it was concluded that remuneration had a significant effect on job satisfaction. This suggested that there was up to 0.474 unit increase in job satisfaction for each unit increase in remuneration. The effect of remuneration was more than 9 times the effect attributed to the error; this was indicated by the t -test value = 9.796. Consistently, Beckery (2011) postulates that pay adequacy has the power to motivate individuals towards higher performance. In a similar vein, a study conducted by Brown (2007) revealed that the amount of remuneration affects the level of job satisfaction among employees. Further support for the study findings is by Shields & Ward (2001) who found that lack of opportunities for career advancement or the possibility of promotion affects job satisfaction among nurses. However, a study conducted by Bender & Heywood (2004) found that university professors who receive high income compared with other jobs had low job satisfaction since they thought that Ph.D. holder who was in the industry earn more than them. It can, therefore, be inferred that such comparisons are detrimental to job satisfaction because of feelings of injustice. In the same way, Bowles, Gintis & Osborne (2001) noted that salary amount is not important for job satisfaction but rather the comparison income the employee uses as a reference point. On the whole, prior studies have indicated that remuneration affects the level of job satisfaction.

Table 5 Effect of Remuneration on Job Satisfaction

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.473	0.131		18.858	0.000
remunerations	0.474	0.048	0.574	9.796	0.000
R Square	0.33				
Adjusted R Square	0.326				
F	95.96				
Sig.	.000b				

a Dependent Variable: job satisfaction

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂) stated that promotion had no significant effect on job satisfaction. The research hypothesis was rejected basing on $\beta_2 = 0.435$ (p-value = 0.000 which was less than $\alpha = 0.05$). Furthermore, the effect of promotion was stated by the t-test value = 8.066 which implied that the standard error associated with the parameter was less than the effect of the parameter. Cognate to the results, Kosteas (2009) echoes that job promotion can have a significant impact on other job characteristics such as responsibilities and subsequent job satisfaction. Similarly, (Clark, 2001) notes that employees may value promotion since it is associated with job amenities such as a bigger office or an ego boost hence they may prompt job satisfaction. Furthermore, a study conducted by Francis, Cadsby, Bram, & Song (2007), revealed that workers value promotion since it is a show of reward for eliciting greater effort hence leading to greater job satisfaction. In addition, Das, (2002) opines that promotions should be provided by every organization to the deserving, qualified and competent employees in order to enhance job satisfaction. Finally, Pergamit & Veum (1999) state that job promotion has a significant effect on job satisfaction of the workers.

Table 6 Effect of Promotion on Job Satisfaction

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.446	0.159		15.389	0.000
promotion	0.435	0.054	0.5	8.066	0.000
R Square	0.25				
Adjusted R Square	0.246				
(ANOVA) F	65.061				
Sig.	.000				

a Dependent Variable: job satisfaction

Conclusion And Recommendations

In conclusion, remuneration has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Consequently, pay adequacy provides the resources needed to meet individual goals thereby enhancing a strong sense of belonging to the school. However, for employees to be satisfied with their job, factors such as age, level of education and experience have to be put into consideration. For instance, an employee would not be satisfied with their job if they believe that others working in the same institution with similar qualifications earn more than them. In this context, job satisfaction is influenced by the comparison income the employee uses as a reference point.

The findings of the study have shown that promotion has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This is in line with prior studies (Pergamit & Veum (1999); Das, (2002); Francis, Cadsby, Bram, & Song (2007) that have shown that promotion has a significant effect on job satisfaction. It can, therefore, be inferred that job promotion can be an effective mechanism in stimulating greater effort among workers. In this context, promotion can be used as a reward for highly productive workers who exert greater effort.

The study has established that remuneration has a positive influence on job satisfaction. Therefore to enhance job satisfaction, there is a need for pay adequacy. However, it would be important to consider factors such as age, education level, and experience to heighten job satisfaction. There is, therefore, need to ensure that employees are fairly remunerated and paid by the national government like other civil servants. Employees' qualification together with experience needs to be commensurate to their pay at all levels of the organization to enhance job satisfaction. Further, the board of management should pay attention to remuneration. Specifically, employees need to have an opportunity for career advancement, which includes the provision of a clear scheme of service where the non-teaching can utilize their talents and skills as their progress in the school setting. In so doing, the schools will foster a healthy and safe working environment that will boost the job satisfaction levels of the non-teaching staff. It also recommended that non-teaching staff is allowed to join trade unions which will agitate for the betterment of their working environment.

This study focused on the effects of working environment on job satisfaction among non-teaching staff in secondary schools in Keiyo South Sub-County. It can be replicated with a larger, more representative sample. Furthermore, it would be interesting to know whether the observed findings hold for other Counties. More research is needed in this subject area to fully establish the effect of promotion and training and development on job satisfaction since the respondents exhibited a lot of uncertainty. Further, replication studies should consider insights from this study influencing job satisfaction including the five factors: 1) remuneration; 2) communication; 3) training and development; 4) promotion and leadership style.

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